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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

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ZAYTUN DARAXTI (*Olea europaea*) DORIVOR XUSUSIYATLARI VA FARMASEFTIKADAGI O'RNI

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Annotatsiya: Zaytun daraxti (*Olea europaea*) qadimdan oziq-ovqat va dorivor manba sifatida qadrlanadi. Uning barglari, mevasi va yog'i farmasevtikada keng qo'llanilib, yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari, diabet va yallig'lanish bilan bog'liq holatlarni davolashda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Ushbu tezis zaytun daraxtining farmasevtikadagi o'rini tahlil qilib, uning turli kasalliklarni davolashdagi samaradorligini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Zaytun daraxti, *Olea europaea*, farmasevtika, zaytun bargi ekstrakti, yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari, diabet, yallig'lanishga qarshi, antioksidant.

Zaytun daraxti insoniyat tarixida muhim o'rin tutib, uning mahsulotlari oziq-ovqat va tibbiyot sohalarida keng qo'llaniladi. So'nggi yillarda zaytun mahsulotlarining farmakologik xususiyatlari va ularning turli kasalliklarni davolashdagi roli bo'yicha ilmiy tadqiqotlar ko'paydi.

Zaytun barglari qadimdan turli kasalliklarni davolashda ishlatilgan. Ularning tarkibida oleuropein, hydroxytyrosol kabi polifenollar mavjud bo'lib, bu moddalar antioksidant, yallig'lanishga qarshi, antibakterial va antiviral ta'sirlarga ega. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, zaytun bargi ekstrakti qon bosimini pasaytirish, yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari xavfini kamaytirish va immunitetni mustahkamlashda samarali hisoblanadi.[1] Zaytun bargi ekstraktining diabet va metabolik sindromga ta'siri. Zaytun bargi ekstrakti qondagi glyukoza miqdorini kamaytirish va insulin sezgirligini oshirish orqali diabetni boshqarishda yordam berishi mumkin. Hayvonlar ustida o'tkazilgan tadqiqotlar zaytun bargi ekstrakti qandli diabetning ayrim belgilarini yaxshilashini ko'rsatgan. Biroq, bu boradagi klinik tadqiqotlar cheklangan va qo'shimcha izlanishlar talab etiladi.[2] Zaytun bargi ekstrakti yurak-qon tomir tizimiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin.

Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, zaytun bargi ekstrakti qon bosimini pasaytirish va yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari xavfini kamaytirishda yordam berishi mumkin. Biroq, bu boradagi klinik tadqiqotlar cheklangan va qo'shimcha izlanishlar talab etiladi.[3] Zaytun bargi ekstrakti yallig'lanishga qarshi va antioksidant ta'sirga ega bo'lib, bu xususiyatlari uni artrit kabi yallig'lanish bilan bog'liq kasalliklarni davolashda foydali qiladi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, zaytun bargi ekstrakti yallig'lanishni kamaytirish va og'riqni yengillashtirishda samarali bo'lishi mumkin. Biroq, bu boradagi klinik tadqiqotlar cheklangan va qo'shimcha izlanishlar talab etiladi. Bundan tashqari, zaytun bargidan tayyorlangan ekstrakt bakteriyalarga qarshi ta'sir ko'rsatib, organizmdagi patogen mikroorganizmlarni kamaytirishga yordam beradi. Ayniqsa, *Staphylococcus aureus* va *Escherichia coli* kabi zararli

bakteriyalarga qarshi samarali ekani isbotlangan [1] Xususan, zaytun bargi ekstrakti arterial qon bosimini nazorat qilish, xolesterin miqdorini kamaytirish va yurak mushaklari faoliyatini yaxshilashga yordam beradi. Bu ta'sirlar, ayniqsa, gipertenziya bilan kasallangan bemorlar uchun foydali hisoblanadi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, zaytun bargi ekstrakti muntazam iste'mol qilinsa, yurak ishemik kasalliklari va insult xavfini kamaytirishi mumkin [3].

Xulosa qilib aytganda, *Olea europaea* va uning mahsulotlari, ayniqsa barglari, farmasevtikada katta ahamiyatga ega. Ularning tarkibidagi bioaktiv birikmalar turli kasalliklarni davolashda qo'llaniladi. Biroq, zaytun mahsulotlarining farmakologik ta'sirlarini to'liq tushunish va ularning xavfsizligini ta'minlash uchun qo'shimcha klinik tadqiqotlar o'tkazish zarur.

Foydalangan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Yaseen Khan, Siddharth Panchal, Niraj Vyas, Ameer Butani, Vimal Kumar *Olea europaea*: a phyto-pharmacological review *Pharmacognosy Reviews* 1 (1), 114-118, 2007
2. Sedef N El, Sibel Karakaya Olive tree (*Olea europaea*) leaves: potential beneficial effects on human health *Nutrition reviews* 67 (11), 632-638, 2009
3. Eddo Rugini, Massimo Mencuccini, Rita Biasi, Maria Maddalena Altamura Olive (*Olea europaea* L.) Protocol for somatic embryogenesis in woody plants, 345-360, 2005